

QUIZ**LAST NAME: ODONG****FIRST NAME: MICHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. What makes academic essay writing different from other form of writing?**
 - Academic writing is well- articulated with simple language that are easy to understand and comprehend.
 - Academic essay writing should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from an academic text or credible sources¹.**
 - Should have footnotes on all the pages.
 - It should give a holistic information about the subject being written on.

- 2. What makes a successful researcher?**
 - Ability to identify strong evidence to support the claims.
 - How well he gathers and analysis data.

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Course pack* (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015), 1.

- How clearly you report your reasoning so that readers can test and judge it before making claim part of their knowledge and understanding².**
- Be able to come out with a clear and precise research question.
3. **Why do researchers rely on the working hypothesis or research questions to guide their work?**
- Working hypothesis help researcher to think ahead, especially about the kind of evidence that will need to support their claims³.**
- Because if you cannot find a working hypothesis or research question, the research project will fail.
- Because when a researcher finds a working hypothesis, they will not need to waste much time looking for other plausible answers to the question, only focus on data collection and completing the research.
- Because working hypothesis feeds into the research questions.
4. **Why should a researcher think about the readers when determining the data sources to answer research questions?**
- Readers belief more on secondary data sources, especially the once that has been published on a recognize sites.
- Because readers only belief in primary data sources to be more reliable since data can be collected in many ways.

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Booth Wayne C. et al., (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

³ Turabian, 21.

- Because readers expect the researcher to use different levels of sources, called primary, secondary and tertiary.**
- Because most readers may already know the answers to the question.
5. **The argument involves exchange or expression of diverging or opposing views, typically in a heated or angry way. What makes research argument less intimidating?**
- It relies on claims of which most of them might be the main focus of the study.
- It assembles an amicable conversation in which you and your immediate readers reason together to solve a problem whose solution they do not yet fully accept⁴.**
- Because the researcher is lone and can manage his/her emotion.
- Less intimidating because it gives room for multi-directional reasoning.
6. **The elements and formatting of a citation may vary, although they all serve the same purpose. What is the main aim of citation in research work?**
- To give readers the information they need to identify and find a source⁵.**
- To show the citation style used by the researcher.
- To show how widely the researcher search for information to answer the research questions.
- It helps researcher to closely track the scope of his inquiry.

⁴ Turabian, 36.

⁵ Turabian, 87.

7. **Getting ready for dissertation work requires being organized in managing the research project well. What do you consider as the initial step preparation to succeed in the dissertation process?**

- Choosing a qualitative research approach and ensuring you have the right advisor.
- Organizing and managing your project, and identifying and developing a researchable topic⁶.**
- Developing research proposal and establishing a timeline.
- Having a clearly laid out guidelines for writing your research ahead of time.

8. **Research approach is directly tied to research problem and purpose. What are the steps in formulating a research approach?**

- Identify the strategy or tradition, then assess the knowledge claims⁷.**
- Modify the research problem to come up with research approach.
- Involve multiple data collection methods to determine the approach.
- Determine the research tradition to use before agreeing on the possible research approach to adopt.

9. **In WHO style, how does the footnote for very short note such as cross-reference to other sections or page documented?**

- Just only use a superscript with the details in the footnote.
- The WHO style provides a flexibility to use superscripts that are either Arabic numerals or figures in documenting footnotes.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, (SAGE Publications Inc., November 28, 2008), 3–5.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 8.

- They should be given in parentheses in the text and also included as footnote references at the bottom of the same page⁸.
- It is structured the same way like any other footnotes, with no parentheses in the text, only the superscript and footnote at the bottom of the page.
10. The WHO style emphasizes the use of non-discriminatory language or non-sexist language. Which of the statements listed below meets the requirement of WHO style?
- A person with physical disabilities⁹ .
- Each research is responsible for writing his or her own report.
- Research scientists often neglect their wives and children.
- A male nurse conducted the examination.

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⁸ World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual, World Health Organization.*,2004, 9, http://www.ianphi.org/_includes/documents/sections/toolkit/who_style-guide.pdf.(accessed December 22,2019)

⁹ World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual, World Health Organization*, 2004, 58.

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